

Potentiometric Studies on the Ternary Systems : Rare Earth Metal Ions-Cyclohexanediamine Tetraacetic Acid-Dicarboxylic Acids

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Mixed-ligand complex formation in the systems: M(III)-CDTA-Dicarboxylic acids (H_2A) [where M(III)=La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) or Dy(III); CDTA=cyclohexanediamine-tetraacetic acid and Dicarboxylic acids (H_2A)=phthalic acid (PHA) or malonic acid (MLA), has been discussed and the formation of 1:1:1 M(III)-CDTA-PHA/MLA species evidenced. The formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) and free energies of formation (ΔG°) for the resulting ternary chelates have been evaluated. The relative order of stabilities in terms of metal ions: La(III)<Pr(III)<Nd(III)<Gd(III)<Dy(III) and in terms of dicarboxylic acids, PHA>MLA has been observed.

RECENTLY the mixed-ligand complexes of some rare earth metals with aminopoly carboxylic acids: IMDA, NTA, HEDTA, EDTA or DTPA¹⁻⁶ and number of dicarboxylic acids have been reported and the expansion of the co-ordination number²⁻⁸ of lanthanide ions evidenced. The pH-metric studies on the systems: M(III)-CDTA-Dicarboxylic acids (H_2A) [where M(III)=La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) or Dy(III); CDTA=cyclohexanediamine-tetraacetic acid and dicarboxylic acids (H_2A) phthalic acid (PHA) or malonic acid (MLA)] have been carried out. The results of these investigations have been presented and discussed.

Experimental

Materials: The solutions of the chemicals viz., metal nitrates, dicarboxylic acids, etc. (AnalaR, BDH or E.Merck grade) were prepared and standardized as described earlier¹⁻³. The solution of tri-potassium salt of CDTA was prepared by dissolving the calculated weighed amount of acid in the required volume of standardized potassium hydroxide solution.

Instrument: The pH-metric measurements were carried out by Philips pH meter (PR 9405 M) which was standardized against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate for pH=4 at 27±1°. The ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M KNO_3$), total volume (50 ml) and the concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) in metal and ligand were kept constant at the beginning of the titration. The pHs were plotted against m (moles of base added per mole of metal ion/ligand).

Calculation: The method of Chaberek and Martell⁹ was employed for calculating the ionisation constants of the ligands (Table 1). The formation

constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) of the resulting ternary species were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹⁰ using expression 1 and free energies of formation by expression 2. The calculated values are recorded in Table 2

TABLE 1		
Ligand	pK_1	pK_2
CDTA	11.41 ± 0.19	—
PHA	2.82 ± 0.07	5.75 ± 0.08
MLA	2.69 ± 0.04	5.35 ± 0.07

$$K_{MLL'} = \frac{T_M - (1/2) A \cdot X}{(1/2)^3 A^3 X} \quad \dots (1)$$

where total free ligand concentration,

$$A = \frac{2T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+]}{2[H^+]/K_1 + K_1} \quad \text{and} \quad X = 1 + \frac{2[H^+]}{K_1 + K_1'}$$

T_{OH} = base used, T_M = total metal ion concentration, K_1 = dissociation constant of CDTA and K_1' = first dissociation constant of PHA/MLA

$$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log K_{MLL'} \quad \dots (2)$$

where ΔG° = free energy of formation (in K cal/degree/mole)

R = gas constant (1.987 cal/degree/mole)
T = temperature on absolute scale.

Results and Discussion

The curves for the systems involving all the rare earth metal ions studied herein, having been identical, those (in Figs. 1 & 2) for the systems La(III)-CDTA-PHA/MLA have only been discussed as representative for the brevity's sake.

An inflection at $m \approx 2.5$ and the formation of a white precipitate (curve a Fig. 1) observed during the titration of La(III) nitrate may be attributed to the basic salt formation¹¹⁻¹².

No well-defined inflection in the curve b (Fig. 1) depicting the titration of tripotassium salt of CDTA has been observed. This may probably be attributed to the non-labile nature of the remaining carboxyproton of the tripotassium salt of CDTA even in the high pH range.

The inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ curve c (Fig 1) (for PHA) and Fig. 2 (for MLA) may be correlated to the stepwise replacement of the two carboxyprotons of the acids during the titration.

Binary Systems : La(III)-CDTA : An extensive lowering in pH, a sharp inflection at $m=1$ (curve d Fig. 1) and non-formation of precipitate during the titration of 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA solution, may be ascribed to the formation of a soluble 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA binary complex⁶.

La(III)-PHA/MLA : The lowering in pH (between

$m=1$ and 2) denoted by the curve e representing the titration of an equimolar binary mixture La(III)-PHA (Fig. 1) and La(III)-MLA (Fig. 2) may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 La(III)-PHA/MLA binary complex. Another sharp inflection at $m \approx 4$ and appearance of a solid phase at $m > 2$ may be correlated to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1 : 1 binary complex into 1 : 3 La(III)-PHA/MLA complex and the metal hydroxide²⁻⁴.

Ternary systems : La(III)-CDTA-PHA/MLA : The curve f representing the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-PHA (Fig. 1) and 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-MLA (Fig. 2) systems depict the lowering in pH from the very beginning indicating the complex formation. Initially a protonated 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-PHA/MLA species (I) is probably formed as indicated by the first inflection at $m=2$. The second sharp inflection at $m=3$ ($pH > 7$) may be ascribed to the deprotonation of (I). The non-superimposable nature of the curve f to either of the curves d and e respectively for binary 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA and 1 : 1 La(III)-PHA/MLA systems and absence of any solid phase during the titration give additional support to the formation of a soluble and stable 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-PHA/MLA ternary species.

Formation Constants of the Ternary Chelates :

The calculated values of the formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) and free energies of formation (ΔG°) for the ternary complexes are recorded in Table 2. The relative order of stability in terms of metal ions : La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III) may probably be attributed to the decreasing size and increasing charge/radius ratio of the metal ions and in terms of acids : PHA > MLA to the presence of a benzene ring in PHA.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\log K_{MLL'}$) AND FREE ENERGIES OF FORMATION (ΔG° IN Kcal/degree/mole) AT $27 \pm 1^\circ$

Metal ions	M(III)-CDTA-PHA		M(III)-CDTA-MLA	
	$\log K_{MLL'}$	ΔG°	$\log K_{MLL'}$	ΔG°
La(III)	5.19 ± 0.09	-7.125	4.82 ± 0.14	-6.616
Pr(III)	5.29 ± 0.09	-7.263	5.06 ± 0.12	-6.947
Nd(III)	5.37 ± 0.10	-7.372	5.15 ± 0.13	-7.069
Gd(III)	5.54 ± 0.08	-7.605	5.39 ± 0.11	-7.316
Dy(III)	5.62 ± 0.09	-7.714	5.47 ± 0.12	-7.509

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